

Preparation and Use of Denatured, De-esterified Hemin as Membrane Electrode for Measurement of Multiionic Potentials of (i) $S_2O_3^{2-}/S_2O_3^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$, (ii) $S_2O_4^{2-}/S_2O_4^{2-}-HPO_4^{2-}$ and (iii) $HPO_4^{2-}/HPO_4^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$ Systems in Aqueous and Aquo-dioxane Media

DEEPAK SHET, JYOTI SHIRODKAR, M. G. SHET* and D. R. PANDIT**

Bharatiya Vidya Bhavans, Bhavan's College Chemistry R & D Centre, Department of Chemistry, Andheri (West), Bombay-400 058

Manuscript received 19 May 1995, revised 10 December 1995, accepted 7 March 1996

We reported earlier¹ the mobility ratios, bionic potentials in aqueous and aquo-methanolic media of $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} anionic systems. In the present work, multiionic potential (M.I.P.) for (i) $S_2O_3^{2-}/S_2O_3^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$, (ii) $S_2O_4^{2-}/S_2O_4^{2-}-HPO_4^{2-}$ and (iii) $HPO_4^{2-}/HPO_4^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$ systems have been studied by using membrane electrodes of denatured de-esterified collodian membrane electrodes in aqueous and aquo-dioxanic media containing 10, 30 and 50% (v/v) of dioxane at constant ionic strength using electrolytic solutions of $Na_2S_2O_3$, $Na_2S_2O_4$ and Na_2HPO_4 at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The values for M.I.P. measurements in aqueous and aquo-dioxanic (Table 1) have been found to be nearly constant in the concentration range 0.001–0.04 M in case of

$S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} ions with various anion-exchanger membrane forms. No other corrections in the activity coefficient data were made as the solutions used were very dilute². Experimental values have been compared with the calculated values (Table 1) obtained from Nernst's equation at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Experimental

Thin and uniform coherent film membranes of varying thickness (0.41–0.43 mm) dried from powdered hemin using collodian as an inert binding material, were prepared for the determination of M.I.P. by using electrolytic solutions of $Na_2S_2O_3$, $Na_2S_2O_4$ and Na_2HPO_4 , containing 10, 30 and 50% (v/v) of dioxane media. An Ajco Verneir potentiometer designed for the measurement of high order accuracy reading of 0.01 mV upto 20 mV was used. The activ-

TABLE 1—MULTIIONIC POTENTIAL MEASUREMENT AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Molarity	0%		10%		30%		50%		
	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	Obs	Cal	
(a) $S_2O_3^{2-}/S_2O_3^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$ system; thickness of film membrane = 0.41 mm :									
0.02 + 0.001	20.48	20.43	20.56	20.50	19.91	19.85	19.66	19.59	
0.02 + 0.003	20.32	20.28	20.39	20.34	–	19.70	–	19.41	
0.02 + 0.004	20.23	20.20	20.31	20.27	–	19.62	19.36	19.32	
0.02 + 0.008	–	19.89	–	19.96	19.35	19.31	18.99	18.97	
0.02 + 0.01	19.77	19.74	–	19.81	19.20	19.16	18.82	18.79	
0.02 + 0.025	18.65	18.62	18.72	18.68	18.07	18.03	17.54	17.51	
(b) $S_2O_4^{2-}/S_2O_4^{2-}-HPO_4^{2-}$ system; thickness of film membrane = 0.43 mm :									
0.02 + 0.001	20.47	20.43	20.55	20.50	19.80	19.85	19.65	19.59	
0.02 + 0.003	20.31	20.28	20.38	20.34	19.74	19.70	19.44	19.41	
0.02 + 0.004	20.23	20.20	–	20.27	19.64	19.62	–	19.32	
0.02 + 0.008	19.92	19.89	19.98	19.96	–	19.31	–	18.97	
0.02 + 0.01	–	19.74	19.84	19.19	19.19	19.16	18.81	18.79	
0.02 + 0.025	18.65	18.62	18.71	18.06	18.06	18.03	17.53	17.51	
(c) $HPO_4^{2-}/HPO_4^{2-}-S_2O_4^{2-}$ systems; thickness of film membrane = 0.47 mm :									
0.02 + 0.001	20.46	20.43	20.54	20.50	19.89	19.85	19.64	19.59	
0.02 + 0.003	20.31	20.28	–	20.34	19.73	19.70	19.45	19.41	
0.02 + 0.004	–	20.20	20.29	20.27	19.63	19.62	19.34	19.32	
0.02 + 0.008	–	19.89	–	19.96	–	19.31	18.98	18.97	
0.02 + 0.01	19.75	19.74	19.83	19.81	19.18	19.16	–	18.79	
0.02 + 0.025	18.64	18.62	18.70	18.68	–	18.03	–	17.51	

**Since deceased

ity coefficients of $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} ions in aqueous media were obtained from titration³ and the activity coefficients in case of aquo-dioxanic media were obtained using Debye-Hückel limiting equation⁴ after making required correction for dielectric constant of aquo-organic solutions for the exchanger.

References

1. M. G. SHET and D. R. PANDIT, *J Indian Chem Soc* 1994, 71 769
2. M. ADHIKARI, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1963, 40, 273.
3. B. C. CONWAY, "Conway Electrochemical Data", Elsevier, New York, 1952.
4. HARNED and OWEN, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 3rd. ed., Reinhold, New York.